

Enhancing Teacher Professional Development through AQAD: A Statewide Implementation

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Abstract:

To ensure that children continue to develop deeper learning and do not succumb to rote practices, it is important that children are often engaged on high rigour questions in a low stakes environment that can also build curiosity, participation and overall exposure to high standards assessments. With this intent, the AQAD offering (An ASSET-Question-A-Day) was provided freely to the state through Gujarat state's app G-Shala. The G-Shala is an App designed for students and teachers as an open platform. Through the AQAD offering, each day, a question per class(3 to 10) for specific subject (Amongst English, Maths, Science, Social Science) was flashed for children/teachers to attempt without any in-app purchases or access restrictions. The aim of this initiative was to (1) expose the children to high quality assessment questions which encourage deeper thinking with understanding; (2) give teachers the suggestive exposure to quality assessment questions. The data was collected and analysed monthly to identify learning gaps that can inform the state on the necessary actions (remedial activities) to tailor classroom strategies for interaction. The data insights were also presented through posters and articles that were published in GCERT's "Jeeven Shikshan" learning magazine for teachers to spread awareness amongst the teacher fraternity as well as educational authorities to gain a comprehensive understanding of student performance and possible ways of remediating them. Thus, we can also achieve professional development for teaching. This practice has continued for the past 3 years, and the paper also talks about the ways of working at scaling solutions with the Government. The paper discusses the data trends, the insights and dissemination and the challenges faced currently in scaling and sustaining it further.

Introduction:

Teacher professional development plays a crucial role in improving educational outcomes for students. [1] As one of the ways to inculcate critical thinking & reasoning in the children, asking high-rigour questions at low-stakes environment; such as Classroom questions represent a potentially powerful tool for interacting with students and stimulating critical thinking. [2]

Teacher professional development plays a crucial role in enhancing instructional practices and improving student outcomes. A lifelong learning approach requires opportunities and incentives for professional development throughout the career to enable staff to refresh, develop and broaden their knowledge and understanding of teaching and to improve their skills and practices. [3]

As one of the tools for teachers to ensure the learning with understanding, Ei had come up with a program "AQAD (ASSET-Question-A-Day)", which ensures the regular exposure to the High-quality assessment questions from their pool of learning assessment program "ASSET". This paper explores the implementation and impact of the AQAD initiative, which aimed to enhance teacher professional development by providing regular exposure to high-quality assessment

questions, identify the common misconceptions out of the received attempts, and strategize the classroom interactions accordingly.

In addition, implementing data-driven classroom modification empowers educators to make informed instructional decisions based on student performance data. Using data to inform teaching practices allows teachers to identify areas of improvement within class as well as individual levels, and tailor personalized instructions to individual student needs, and promote a more personalized learning experience.[4]

In the current paper, we explore the uptake of AQAD questions by both teachers as well as students of Gujarat state through the state build App that helped them continue to learn and understand gaps in the learning. The primary objectives of the AQAD initiative were to expose students to high-quality assessment questions and provide teachers with valuable resources for classroom instruction. We try and review the overall approach and faced challenges in the process.

2. Design and Development Principles:

Ei ASSET evaluates a student's level of understanding by asking unfamiliar and thought-provoking questions that assess the student's basic understanding of concepts. This prevents a system of rote learning and encourages students to understand topics in depth. In order to ensure the impact of Ei ASSET high quality questions to a larger audience, the idea of AQAD was developed, where one ASSET question was released on the individual site (<https://www.aqad.in/?language=en>). Students as well as teachers can attempt the question, along with their explanation for free everyday. Overall, the design and development of the AQAD initiative were grounded in research-based principles that promote effective learning and assessment practices. This section outlines the key principles and strategies employed in creating the question bank and integrating it into the G-Shala app.

3. Implementation Details:

Fig. 1 AQAD website, open for access to every child & teacher

he successful implementation of the AQAD initiative required collaboration between educational authorities, technology developers, and teachers. Ei publishes AQAD questions everyday on their individual website in English : <https://www.aqad.in/?language=en>. (Fig. 1) However, in Gujarat, Educational Initiatives provided questions in Gujarati context, testing the same objectives on the "G-shala" app."G-Shala" is an acronym for "Gujarat Students' Holistic Adaptive Learning" App, acting as an education and reference application. It is created with the purpose of helping nurture the students from Standard 1 to 12 of government and aided schools. The app is governed by Gujarat Council of School Education, Samagra Shiksha,

Education Department, Government of Gujarat based on Gujarat State Education Board (GSEB) syllabus. G-Shala is a platform-agnostic and device-independent app that provides digital interactives, 2D/3D augmented e-content mapped with textbooks for all the subjects and caters to grades 5-12. It is based on the Gujarat State Education Board (GSEB) syllabus. It was launched by Govt. in the wake of Covid-19, to ensure that the learning does not stop for govt. school children despite the lockdown extremities.

The process steps for the implementation of AQAD questions on G-shala are presented in the chart (fig.2)

Fig. 2 Process flow of Implementing AQAD questions on G-shala app

The questions were displayed on the G-shala app upon login. Whenever a child or a teacher logged in the app for the first time in the day, they received the AQAD question as a pop-up (as seen in the image below : fig. 3). They were asked to select the correct option for the questions posed to them. They had the liberty not to attend the question by closing the pop-up.

Fig. 3 AQAD question being displayed on G-shala app

The questions were given specifically in the login IDs for classes 3 to 10; and for each day, a specific subject was decided for the question as followed:

- Monday - English (For classes 3-10)
- Tuesday and Thursday - Mathematics (For classes 3-10)
- Wednesday and Friday - Science (For classes 3-10)

- Saturday - Social Science (For classes 5-10)

4. Evaluation of Effectiveness:

To assess the effectiveness of the AQAD initiative, data was collected and analyzed on a monthly basis. The findings from the evaluation are discussed, highlighting the positive impact of AQAD on student learning outcomes.

At Ei's end, the data was observed in more filtered way, where they determined 3 parameters to look upon:

1. Total attempts of students on a particular question
2. Students' overall performance in the question
3. Option-wise percentage distribution of students' attempts - to observe the number of students attempting other options and generate misconception insights out of them.

Sr No.	Date	Question	Correct Answer	AQAD Performance						SchoolNet Performance					
				N	Overall (%)	A (%)	B (%)	C (%)	D (%)	N	Overall (%)	A (%)	B (%)	C (%)	D (%)
1	02-08-2022	x is an integer and $5 - x > 15$. The largest possible value that x can take is A: 10 B: -10 C: -11 D: 15	C	31	70.97	6.45	12.90	70.97	9.68	98	17	17	36	17	30
2	03-08-2022	A TV programme's live telecast starts in India at 4:30 PM (local time) and starts at 7:00 PM (local time) in	C	31	38.71	19.35	9.68	38.71	32.26	96	23	28	43	23	6

Fig. 4 AQAD dashboard used for observing daily data

We handled the review process of this data, to identify common patterns of answering by students; to generate particular misconceptions in the skills/ sub skills of the particular subject. (fig. 4)

Out all of the questions asked in the month, the misconceptions in a particular skills/ sub skills of the subject learning were identified and presented by Ei through 2 different ways:

1. Creating a statistical & analytic report; intended for educational authorities, educators
2. Misconception posters; intended for educators or coordinators to strategizing the classroom interactions accordingly

Both of these methods contained "Misconception Explanation and Remedial Instructions" writing; which are beneficial for authorities, educators, teachers to identify the learning/ understanding gaps seen in the students, and strategize the interactions in the class accordingly, in order to rectify the misconceptions.

5. Insights from AQAD students' attempts and Recommendations:

Based on the insights derived from the data analysis and evaluation, the key findings and lessons learned from the AQAD initiatives were quite astonishing in terms of the exposure of misconceptions that are hindering the learning of the students.

S no.	Subject - Class	Questions with students data	Misconception observed
1	Science - 8	<p>The gas that is present in MAXIMUM quantity in the air we EXHALE is...</p> <p>A. Nitrogen (14%) B. Oxygen (12%) C. Carbon dioxide (71%) D. Argon (3%)</p>	<p>Only 14% of students were able to choose the right option. A common understanding is responsible for this, that humans emit "only CO₂" (carbon dioxide) in the form of exhalation. But, in reality, it only releases a mixture of gases, which contain a large amount of CO₂. This understanding turns into "misunderstanding", and they choose option C.</p> <p>Exhaled air mixtures also contain the highest amount of nitrogen as outside air, and 14% of students who understand this concept prefer Option A.</p>
2	Mathematics - 7	<p>What number will fit in the empty box to make the given number sentence true?</p> <p>$-4 - (-5) = -5 + ?$</p> <p>A. -4 (35%) B. 4 (21%) C. -6 (27%) D. 6 (17%)</p>	<p>To answer the given question, students should have an understanding of whole numbers, and be able to add and subtract positive and negative integers. 35% of the students who chose option A might not have noticed the (-) sign appearing twice in the subtraction question. 21% of the students who chose option B might not know the difference between addition and subtraction of whole numbers. 27% and 17% of the students who chose options C and D have increased or decreased one unit by comparing the number to the left, irrespective of the sign.</p>
3	Social Science - 9	<p>'Drip irrigation' is an irrigation system in which water is slowly applied to the roots of plants through a network of pipes. This is one of the traditional water harvesting systems in Northeast India, where bamboo pipes are interconnected to form such a network. For what type of farming is this method best suited?</p>	<p>The question checks the knowledge of the crops grown especially in the northeast and other parts of India.</p> <p>Students choosing option A are using the recall of rice being one of the major crops of Northeast India, however, they failed to recall that rice or paddy saplings are planted in flooded soil making drip irrigation an incorrect answer.</p> <p>Students choosing option B have correctly connected pepper with Meghalaya where drip irrigation is used to grow this spice.</p> <p>Students choosing option C have not connected coconut being a plantation crop which cannot be easily grown in the hills.</p> <p>Students choosing option D have a gap in learning that bamboo, though a northeastern crop, requires a large amount of water in its</p>

		<p>A. Rice (42%) B. Pepper (20%) C. Coconut (8%) D. Bamboo (30%)</p>	initial period of growth.
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Table 1: Questions showing option-wise students' attempts in percentage and the misconceptions highlighted through them by Ei

These misconceptions were highlighted along with the remedial activities for it through formal reports, as well as the misconception posters (Fig. 5). These posters were created in Gujarati language to cater to the teachers through all levels of demography within Gujarat.

Fig. 5(a)

Fig. 5(b)

Fig. 5(c)

Fig. 5 Misconception posters of (a) Mathematics (b) Science (c) Social science

These posters were designed by Ei with the thought that "with this poster, an educator can just walk in the classroom, and design the remedial activity on their own using the poster, and clear out the misunderstandings in particular concepts that are challenging the learning in the children." The basic structure of the poster is indicated in the image below (Fig. 6)

Fig. 6 AQAD misconception poster template

The monthly reports were intended more for the educational authorities to check for the awareness of the initiative within the students & administration, and it provided the overall status of the children's learning within the particular subjects. It also had recommendations/suggestions on the administration, on how they can permeate the learning through providing better system and procedures.

Although for Gujarat, these posters were shared with GCERT (Gujarat Council of Educational Research and Training); other state boards whom Ei is supporting in setting up State Assessment Cells, or board reforms (such as : AP-SALT project at Andhra-Pradesh) have received similar posters on their students' attempts data for teacher training, and the responses have been impactfully positive.

6. Scaling and Sustainability Challenges:

While the AQAD initiative has demonstrated promising results, scaling and sustaining it on a statewide level pose several challenges.

- The first challenge comes up with the availability of the proper platform. In Gujarat, AQAD is run on the app, which is comparatively more accessible to the students on daily basis, rather than the site. It is evident from AQAD Nagaland program run by Ei, where the students have to follow tedious steps to reach on AQAD Site: Go to Nagaland education board site >> Select AQAD >> get redirected to AQAD site >> Attempt the question.

As a result, the maximum number of attempts visits received on the site from Nagaland has been 67, which is insufficient to generate learning insights.

fig. 6 Snapshot from Google analytics for AQAD site, where the yellow line indicates the number of visits from Nagaland region on the site; and the blue line suggests the

overall visits from everywhere on the site

- The second major challenge for the scaling up is the data infrastructure for receiving, segregating the data for different clients through multiple client specific sites/platforms; which can be considered as an internal challenge from Ei's end, and can be mitigated with proper dedicated team for the whole program. However, this requires support from the client (state educational boards; in the majority of the cases) to provide support & show sufficient interest from time to time.
- Overall, this requires active interest among teachers/educational authorities to propagate the final outputs (reports, posters) into the rightful hands of educators, who can execute the remedial instructions with the help of these outputs. Ei's role in making this possible can also occur through continuous engagement with the officials & supporting their technical architecture for the process wherever needed. As observed from the annual data collected from G-shala, There also comes decline in the number of students attempts from time to time; especially during term-end examinations, holiday seasons, and vacations. Even apart from these; we can see the number of students' attempts is at average. Although the number of students' attempts that we receive, the average number of attempts received on the monthly basis is way less compared to the potential reach that can occur through G-shala.

Table 2: Month- statistics of AQAD questions for year 2022-23

Subjects	Sum of Total questions shared	Sum of Total attempts	Sum of Highest attempts received on a question	Sum of Lowest Attempts received on a question	Sum of Questions highlighting misconceptions
Mathematics	908	64471	3934	254	353
Science	857	61814	3969	155	357
Social Science	310	28379	3410	459	111
Grand Total	2075	154664	11313	868	821

Subject	Average of Total attempts per month	Average of Highest attempts received on a question per month	Average of Lowest Attempts received on a question per month	Average of Questions highlighting misconceptions per month
Mathematics	4605	281	20	25
Science	4415	284	11	26
Social Science	2027	244	33	8

Table 3: Average monthly statistics, highlighting the reach & impact of AQAD program in Gujarat

Conclusion:

The AQAD initiative has proven to be a valuable tool for enhancing teacher professional development and promoting deeper learning among students. By providing regular access to high-quality assessment questions, teachers and students alike benefit from improved instructional practices and enhanced academic outcomes. However, scaling and sustaining the initiative requires careful consideration of challenges and collaborative efforts. This research paper contributes to the body of knowledge in teacher professional development and provides insights for policymakers, educators, and researchers seeking to implement similar initiatives.

References:

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